
Annual report 2025
*National Strategy for Data Management based
on the FAIR principles*

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Terminology/acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AAAI	Authentication, Authorization and Accounting Infrastructure
ALLEA	All European Academies
AU	Aarhus University
AAU	Aalborg University
CBS	Copenhagen Business School
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
CISO Forum	Chief Information Security Officer Forum
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CSC	IT Center for Science (Finland)
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DeiC	Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
DFF	Independent Research Fund Denmark
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
eiDAS	<i>electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services.</i>
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
ERDA	Electronic Research Data Archive
ESA	European Space Agency
ESO	European Southern Observatory
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFF	Danish National Research Foundation
GIS	Geographic Information System
HPC	High Performance Computing
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IdP	Identity Provider
IFD	Innovationsfund Denmark
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ITU	IT University of Copenhagen
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee (Storbritannien)
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
maDMP	machine-actionable Data Management Plan
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
NCC	National Competence Center
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
REFEDS	Research and Education FEDerations
RAiD	Research Activity Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RUC	Roskilde University
SDU	University of Southern Denmark
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
T&I	Trust & Identity
UFM / UFS	Ministry of Higher Education & Science / Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science
URIS	Committee on Guidelines for International Research and Innovation Cooperation
WAYF	Where Are You From

1. Executive summary

Challenges related to capacity, varying maturity levels, and increasingly complex legal requirements underscore the need for national coordination and shared solutions, with international anchoring through EOSC continuing to drive interoperability. The working groups' results show that FAIR is an ecosystem challenge requiring coherent infrastructure, governance, competencies, security frameworks, and sustained funding. This annual report highlights FAIR implementation in Denmark in 2025 across six areas.

Working Group A – Policies, Tools, and Research Support for FAIR Data Management

The group focused on data management planning tools and researcher support. It identified fragmented research support capacity and recommends consolidating competencies and establishing collaborative structures to strengthen governance and the use of research infrastructures. The working group recommends that the research support function should be reassessed at local and national levels.

Working Group B – Establishing FAIR Infrastructure and Long-Term Preservation

The group recommends three classes of long-term preservation as a common framework to enable more consistent planning. It highlights the need for national agreements on when data should move between local and national infrastructures and for coordinating supporting infrastructures such as metadata catalogues and persistent identifiers. Finally, Denmark should work towards strengthening alignment with European standards.

Working Group C – Financial plan for FAIR data

Funding bodies should implement harmonised Data Management Plan (DMP) requirements based on UFS' guidelines, allowing extraordinary DMP costs to be covered by funders. Standard data management costs should be included in project budgets or overheads, with complex projects budgeting separately. Funding bodies should clearly specify eligible costs in application guidelines.

Working Group D – Plan for structuring and developing FAIR Competencies and Knowledge

The group mapped Denmark's data stewardship landscape, identifying roles, competency gaps, and professional development needs. It continues to explore models for a national competence centre and will, in 2026, examine tools for recognising and rewarding FAIR practices.

Working Group E – Security Aspects of FAIR Data Collaboration

The group reviewed universities' experiences with [URIS](#) guidelines, presents principles for secure data management—including access control, encryption, and anonymisation—and proposes developing a national data classification model. The CISO Forum under Universities Denmark will further develop these principles to support consistent assessment of security solutions for sensitive research data.

Working Group F – Valuation of Data

The group refined a national framework, conducted literature studies and pilot interviews, and is preparing a stakeholder consultation in 2026. This will enhance understanding of data's value and support sustainable FAIR implementation.

Effective tools, standardised practices, transparent funding, and national coordination are central to FAIR implementation and ensure long-term, researcher-centred data management.

2. Introduction

In 2021, the *National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR Principles*¹ was published, serving as a key reference for assessing alignment with the FAIR principles at Danish research institutions. The implementation of the strategy is monitored by the FAIR Reference Group and dedicated working groups. The work has evolved with the addition of a new working group (Valuation of data) and a stronger focus on international alignment, to ensure interoperability in infrastructure and standards for research data management.

In April 2025, The Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science approved *Addendum to the Terms of Reference for the FAIR Reference Group in 2026*², extending its mandate through 2026. This follows a previous extension in 2024, which had prolonged the work until the end of 2025. The addendum introduces several updates: It allows for adjusting or refining focus areas based on progress made so far, and places greater emphasis on knowledge sharing with university leadership, including through an annual joint meeting. It also proposes the development of a monitoring mechanism to track alignment to the strategy. The 2026 annual report will moreover review overall progress since 2021, assess the need for a national competence centre and long-term data preservation solution, and include an evaluation of the FAIR groups' structure. Moving forward, The Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science will annually determine whether the work under the strategy should be extended for another year.

The six working groups include:

- A: Policies, tools and research support for FAIR data management
- B: Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation
- C: Financial plan for FAIR data
- D: Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge
- E: Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration
- F: Valuation of data

Implementing FAIR in practice requires not only technical and procedural expertise, but also awareness of data's value, incentives for FAIR adoption, stakeholder engagement, and secure handling of sensitive data. It is a multidisciplinary effort drawing on diverse professional competencies. To promote coordination and synergy, the working group chairs collaborate to identify overlaps and explore cross-disciplinary opportunities. Effective communication—internally and with the wider university sector—is essential to ensure the strategy's knowledge and recommendations are broadly disseminated.

This annual report presents contributions from each working group, with their reflections on the current state of FAIR implementation at the universities in Denmark.

¹ DeIC. (2021). National strategi for data management baseret på FAIR-principper (2021). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.48715/fm9h-m781>

² Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education, & Danish e Infrastructure Consortium. (2025). Addendum to the Terms of Reference for the FAIR Reference Group in 2026. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15316568>

3. Communication and knowledge exchange on data management and FAIR

Internal and external communication

Goal 0.1. Communication support to be established across the 6 working groups, where members of the working groups can find information about, for example:

- Policies
- Strategies
- Tools
- Q&A Manuals
- International references
- Litterature
- Courses related to FAIR and Data Management

Reporting: Communication channels have been established for the working groups on Microsoft Teams, where members can find information about the above, as well as store agendas, minutes, and other materials, and communicate internally easily, and without disruption.

Goal 0.2: An open and public channel will be established for publication of relevant materials from the working groups and the FAIR Reference group.

Reporting: A channel has been established on Zenodo for the [FAIR strategy](#). The chairpersons of the working groups have internal collaboration and communication about the focus areas to explore interdisciplinary opportunities.

4. Working group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management

Working Group A addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 1, 2, and 3.

Focus area 1

How do different disciplines implement the FAIR principles in research practices? For example, in their specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from/in collaboration with international research environments?

Goal(s):

Present examples of subject-specific workflows and tools from selected disciplines across various academic fields.

Reporting:

The Landscape of Machine-Actionable DMPs (maDMPs) in Denmark: University Context

Working group A has examined the Danish landscape of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs), focusing on universities by conducting a small empirical survey among DeIC front office personnel.

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are increasingly recognised as essential tools for ensuring that research data are managed according to the principles of FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016). They are increasingly recognised as crucial for ensuring long-term access and use of research data and digital objects (Pham et al., 2023). However, in practice, DMPs are often seen as static and administrative rather than as integral to the research process.

To address this gap, the concept of the machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP) has emerged. Machine-actionable DMPs encode information in structured, interoperable formats that can be read and exchanged automatically between systems, repositories, and funders (e.g. HORIZON 2020) (Miksa et al., 2019; Simms et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

Despite funder and institutional mandates, DMPs remain underused and undervalued by researchers. Three interrelated issues explain this limited adoption:

- Administrative burden: DMPs are perceived as compliance documents rather than as living, useful research tools.
- Poor integration: Most DMPs exist outside the systems researchers use daily (e.g., electronic lab notebooks or repositories).
- Lack of automation: Current tools produce text-based outputs that are not machine-readable and cannot exchange metadata across systems.

As a result, DMPs often fail to improve reproducibility, transparency, or data reuse — key objectives of the FAIR movement (Miksa et al., 2019; Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Potential Solutions

Recent years have seen several technological approaches to improving the usefulness and automation of Data Management Plans (DMPs). Two main directions have emerged:

Machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) – the use of structured, machine-readable formats (e.g., JSON, XML) that enable interoperability and metadata exchange between research systems. MaDMPs form the foundation for automating DMP workflows and linking project information across platforms such as repositories and funders.

AI-assisted DMPs – Recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), have introduced new ways to assist in creating and maintaining Data Management Plans (DMPs). AI tools can automatically draft DMPs, adapt content to institutional templates and funder requirements (Karlsen, 2025).

While both approaches contribute to the future of automated research data management, this report focuses primarily on machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs).

Survey of the Danish Landscape

Although the survey represents a small sample, the respondents are likely subject-matter experts within their respective universities, providing a credible snapshot of the national landscape. Despite its limited scale, the survey results present a clear and consistent picture of the current state of maDMP adoption in Denmark.

The findings reveal moderate conceptual awareness but very limited practical implementation of maDMPs. While the [DeiC DMP tool](#) is officially recommended on most Danish university websites (though the actual level of use is unclear, as only 43 plans are publicly available), it does not yet support full machine-actionability or system-level integration. No Danish university currently reports an operational maDMP deployment.

Recommendation(s):

Machine-actionable DMPs represent a promising evolution of the traditional DMP, enabling automation, interoperability, and enhanced compliance with FAIR and Open Science principles.

However, the survey results show that a systematic maDMP implementation has not yet occurred within Danish universities. The current landscape remains fragmented, with conceptual awareness and isolated pilot efforts but without shared infrastructure or coordinated efforts.

To achieve a broader and more sustainable adoption, progress should follow a logical, stepwise trajectory. The first step—demonstrating institutional value through standardised maDMP implementation—is the most crucial, as it will establish the foundation and motivation for all subsequent progress:

- 1. Demonstrate institutional value through standardised maDMP implementation:**

Develop clear, practical use cases based on the [RDA maDMP Common Standard](#) that shows how maDMPs directly benefit researchers. The primary value proposition should be a reduced administrative burden and seamless integration with existing research workflows—for example, automatic DOI generation for datasets and pre-populated sections drawn from university systems (e.g., GDPR registrations, ethical approvals, and budget data). At the same time, administrative units such as IT, HR, Legal, and research support offices can benefit from automated notifications, improved compliance tracking, and consistent GDPR management. Demonstrating this dual value—

researcher efficiency first, institutional coordination second—will give maDMPs real functional relevance and directly address the challenges outlined in the problem statement.

2. Build capacity:

Once standardised institutional value is demonstrated, there will naturally arise a need to strengthen maDMP-related competencies. This includes developing skills among data stewards, research-support staff, and researchers through training, hands-on pilots, and knowledge sharing. Capacity building ensures that institutions can maintain and expand maDMP practices sustainably.

3. Coordinate nationally to consolidate and extend capacity:

As institutions begin to adopt maDMPs more widely, a coordinated national strategy should follow to reinforce and scale local progress. Because all implementations are based on the same RDA standard, national coordination can both support capacity building—for example, through shared training resources, infrastructure, and guidance—and ensure long-term interoperability, harmonisation, and sustainability across Danish institutions.

References:

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Appendices:

[Working Group A: Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Full Report 2025](#)

Focus area 2

What policies and motivating/supportive measures exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?

Goal(s):

Collect and summarise policies and examples of motivating and supporting efforts to access and reuse research data, at universities and selected research institutions.

Reporting:

The Research Support Function at the Local, National and International Level

Modern research is increasingly dependent on advanced digital infrastructures, complex digital data workflows, and high-level technical competencies within computing and data management. This document argues that the Research Support Function (RSF) – particularly its technical dimension – has become a critical prerequisite for research quality, research productivity, and in turn national competitiveness. To use digital technologies in research, solid knowledge about them is necessary, with high probability including subjects like e.g.:

- Data governance and security
- FAIR metadata engineering
- Data quality, preservation, and research infrastructure
- Multi-stakeholder collaboration & organisational capability
- Advanced computing & HPC

Rising Complexity and Growing Skills Gap

Research infrastructures, tools, and services are rapidly increasing in complexity as well as in cost. At the same time methodical data management and FAIR data practices are increasingly necessary, across all disciplines and research agendas, when aiming to be relevant and globally competitive.

Yet the competence within research groups to utilise modern infrastructures, tools, and services and to implement methodical data management and the FAIR principles are often weak or absent. Universities organise and offer the RSF very differently, and to a different extent, but mostly focused on the very basic needs of mainstream science, offering support at lower levels of complexity. It is the exception, rather than the rule, that RSF is offered with capacity for the high-level, generic research infrastructure, services and tools utilisation and development, software engineering and data stewardship, which is required for advanced, cross-border data and computational research.

International Expectations and Strategic Dependencies

European strategies, e.g. the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)³, call for consolidation of technical expertise, e.g. in national competence centres. Participation in European collaborations, Horizon Europe projects, and ESFRI/ERIC infrastructures increasingly depends on what a country can collectively contribute, e.g.: valuable datasets; interoperable digital services; FAIR-aligned data management, and teams of highly skilled technical experts.

Without national coordination of a much stronger RSF, Denmark will fall short of these expected capabilities.

The Need for National Critical Mass of Competence

High-level RSF requires experts – data stewards, software specialists, infrastructure engineers – often at postdoc level or higher, dealing with digital infrastructure issues.

Such experts are a scarce resource in general and not least for universities that are seldom able to offer the going salary of scarce technical experts. Individual universities therefore struggle to recruit and retain these competencies. Heterogeneous local efforts do exist, but they often lead to duplication of effort and uncoordinated support at uneven levels within and across institutions and the national border. This leads to lost opportunity and ultimately weakened international competitiveness. At the same time there is a lack of initiatives to educate enough experts at all competence levels within RSF. It is important to create and sustain research environments that can assist in developing the RSF into an attractive and viable career path.

³ The Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda and its Multi-Annual Roadmap: <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/sria-mar/>

There is a need for stronger national coordination and cooperation on pooling expertise and to standardise practices, professionalise and improve the reuse of tools and services, and to provide on-demand support for research groups with complex digital requirements. Successful models have already been established within a few advanced infrastructures, with e.g. supercomputing centres (HPC) and EuroHPC Competence Centres (EuroCC⁴) as examples.

Recommendation(s):

To support modern data intensive research with heavy computing needs, Denmark must strengthen and modernise the RSF at all levels – local, national and international. This requires:

- Reevaluating local RSF capacity at universities.
- Consolidating high-level RSF competences nationally, i.e. within digital research infrastructures, computing and data management, FAIRification, software engineering, data stewardship.
- Ensuring that Denmark can engage and meet international expectations for infrastructure establishment, interoperability, standardisation, and accompanying advanced support.
- Facilitating, by organising the collaboration and sharing of RSF across institutional and national boundaries.
- Investing in research-based education of more experts to fulfil the demands at all levels.

Without national coordination and a well-organised critical mass of competence, Denmark will remain structurally fragmented, limiting its ability to participate fully in European research infrastructures and to unlock the potential of its research communities.

Use Case: Organising a Research Data Management and Data Science Support Unit

Where the previous section looks at the support function from an overall perspective, this use case focuses on a local example of a model for building a research support function that can cover both general and specialised needs. The section outlines key considerations and a proposed roadmap for establishing Research IT, Research Data Management, and Data Science support within the Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University. It addresses a general national challenge concerning Research IT support, which has been identified at some, but not all, Danish universities. The structures and organisational models described are not yet formally approved by the department's leadership. They represent a synthesis of expressed strategic needs and the results of a bottom-up process involving potential members of the proposed unit.

Roadmap for Organising a Research Data Management and Data Science Support Unit

The establishment of a Data Science Support Unit at the Department of Agroecology involved several key steps, ranging from assessing departmental needs to defining the required competencies and organisational structure. The roadmap followed is summarised below.

Assessing the Department's Needs

We first identified the department's specific challenges and strategic objectives. Agroecology is inherently interdisciplinary, combining ecology, agricultural sciences, and social sciences. We identified research areas where data science would have the greatest impact—such as precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, modelling of ecosystem processes, and sustainability-oriented analyses. Additionally, we engaged with researchers and existing data specialists to map data-related needs across sections.

⁴ EuroCC: https://www.eurohpc-iu.europa.eu/research-innovation/our-projects/eurocc_en

Defining the Scope and Services of the Unit

We identified both specialised and general support needs. Specialised support included data cleaning, modelling, machine learning, geospatial analysis, and advanced analytical workflows, and general support included experimental design, data visualisation, statistical analysis, and data storage solutions (ERDA/SIF). A central question concerned the unit's role: whether it should focus solely on technical assistance or also collaborate on research projects and strategic infrastructure initiatives across sections. Training and education were recognised as essential services, including workshops, seminars, and individual mentoring for researchers, technical staff, and students.

Building the Team: Roles and Expertise

We conducted an internal mapping exercise using a shared skills matrix (Excel) and invited contributions from relevant data scientists, analysts, GIS specialists, data managers/engineers, software developers, and domain experts. Discussions also addressed the involvement of PhD students, postdocs, and potential collaborations with other departments and institutes.

Developing a Data Management Strategy

To ensure robust, secure, and scalable data storage and utilisation (e.g., cloud solutions, databases, ERDA), we drafted a data management strategy aligned with the FAIR principles. Given that agroecological research often involves large and heterogeneous datasets, accessibility and scalability were prioritised. Protocols for data sharing—especially when handling sensitive agricultural or ecological information—were also considered.

Establishing a Collaborative Environment

Regular meetings and a clear communication framework were created to ensure alignment with researchers and department leadership. Effective collaboration between data scientists, agroecologists, and other domain experts is critical for solving complex research problems. A culture of sharing best practices, tutorials, and resources was encouraged to support capacity building across the department.

Governance and Workflow

Discussions on project management and time allocation revealed varying preferences among participants. Some members wished to contribute both to their own research projects and to strategic department level projects. Others preferred focusing exclusively on their own research.

There was broad interest in clear guidelines for data management, coding practices, and project workflows to ensure consistent and high-quality outcomes.

We also discussed metrics for evaluating the unit's performance, such as effectiveness in supporting research projects, number and impact of training activities, and contributions to publications and research outcomes.

Key Benefits to the Department

Strengthening coordination and collaboration across groups and projects is expected to increase analytical capacity, leading to more robust and reproducible research results, improve decision making, enabling researchers and policymakers to base recommendations on more precise analyses regarding agricultural practices, environmental policies, and sustainability strategies and to increase data science literacy across the department, benefitting research, teaching, and student training.

Overall, the Research Data Management and Data Science Support Unit is expected to significantly enhance the department's capacity for research and innovation in agroecology.

Appendices:

[Working Group A: Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Full Report 2025](#)

Focus area 3

Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing overall data responsibility, even after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ceased.

Goal(s):

Identify and recommend best practices for data governance and policies to manage the overall responsibility for data. How can we foster a culture where data sharing and Open Science are the expected standards?

Reporting:

In 2025 working group A has focused on the landscape of machine actionable DMPs and the research support function. Furthermore, the report delivered in 2024, "*Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024*", has been updated and expanded with the full text of the papers on machine actionable DMPs and the research support function. In 2026, working group A plans to continue the work on identifying best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing data responsibility.

Recommendation(s):

Appendices:

5. Working group B – *Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation*

Working Group B addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 4, 5 and 6.

Focus area 4

What infrastructure is available for the long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how is coherence and collaboration ensured between research institutions, DeIC, and the National Archives regarding long-term preservation?

Goal(s):

The goal of this work is to establish a clear, shared understanding of the three classes of long-term research data preservation, including how they differ in purpose, required practices, and current use. Based on this, we provide recommendations to improve dialogue and coordinated planning on long-term preservation among the key stakeholders.

Reporting:

The 2024 findings of Working Group B identified three distinct classes of long-term research data preservation. Subsequent feedback indicated that this division may not have been communicated clearly enough in the previous report. However, the three-class division has held up well and has been further refined through discussions in 2025. The three categories should not be regarded as mutually exclusive, meaning that data may fall under more than one category.

Each class is characterised by its primary purpose:

1. **Preservation for reproducibility and verification**

Data is preserved as-is to ensure availability for audit, replication, and compliance with reproducibility requirements. No operations on the data are required beyond what is necessary to secure its retention and association with dependant publications.

2. **Preservation to support future research and reuse**

Data is accompanied by rich metadata, assigned persistent identifiers (PIDs), and deposited in a Trusted Data Repository that publish bibliographic metadata to search engines to support its findability. Data formats may be adapted to improve usability with contemporary tools within the domain. This category aligns closely with the FAIR principles.

3. **Preservation for posterity**

Data is transformed into formats suitable for long-term logical preservation and curation, ensuring interpretability and accessibility into the distant future.

Preservation for reproducibility and verification

This class of preservation focuses on ensuring that research results can be checked, validated, and independently reproduced. The data is kept exactly as it was used in the original research, unaltered and in its native formats, so that others can follow the same steps and arrive at the same conclusions. This form of preservation underpins academic integrity, as it enables auditors, collaborators, and peers to verify that findings are based on sound analyses and that no crucial data has been lost or changed. It is essential for

satisfying reproducibility requirements from journals, funders, and institutional policies, and for maintaining trust in the scientific record.

This class of preservation primarily retains data in its original form together with the scripts, workflows, and documentation used in the research. Many researchers store this material in institutional storage systems, project folders, or version-controlled repositories (e.g., GitLab) where preservation can be achieved by “freezing” the data as-is and ensuring its retention for the required period. The emphasis is on keeping the exact working environment intact enough to enable later inspection or re-execution. Some publications encourage deposition in general purpose repositories like Zenodo and DeIC Dataverse.

Preservation to support future research and reuse

This class of preservation focuses on ensuring that data remains useful and valuable for future scientific work, both within and beyond the original research domain. To support reuse, data must be described with sufficiently rich metadata, assigned persistent identifiers, and deposited in Trusted Data Repositories that expose standardised bibliographic metadata, making the data findable and citable. In many cases, data formats may be transformed or normalised to ensure that they remain compatible with contemporary analytical tools, thereby enhancing their practical usability. This approach is closely aligned with the FAIR principles and aims to preserve the scientific value and usability of data over time, enabling new analyses, replication studies, meta-analyses, and interdisciplinary research that build on previously collected datasets.

This class of preservation is the domain of general and thematic data repositories, although a survey conducted by the working group showed that many of these repositories offer unclear guarantees regarding long-term preservation.

DeiC Dataverse has been created as a national infrastructure to host both general and thematic data repositories for the Danish universities. DeiC Dataverse currently guarantees at least 10 years of preservation from the date of deposition. Work is ongoing to explore how this guarantee might be extended. At the time of writing DeiC Dataverse has only been adopted by the University of Copenhagen.

Preservation for posterity

This class of preservation is concerned with ensuring that data remains intelligible and accessible far into the future, long after the original research context, technologies, and tools have disappeared. It often requires transforming data into stable formats suitable for long-term logical preservation and curation, accompanied by metadata that explains how the data was created and how it should be interpreted. Unlike preservation aimed at reproducibility or short-term reuse, preservation for posterity acknowledges that future users may not share today’s assumptions, software ecosystems, or disciplinary conventions. Its purpose is to maintain historical continuity, safeguarding data as part of the cultural and scientific heritage so that future generations can understand past research practices, reconstruct historical knowledge, or explore questions that were not foreseeable at the time of collection. This kind of preservation provides the historical continuity needed to understand how scientific knowledge has evolved over time and ensures that data remains interpretable and accessible into the distant future.

The Danish National Archives have a strong national mandate to preserve records of enduring value for the state and society, including research data that meet their appraisal criteria. They operate certified long-term preservation infrastructures and follow strict legal and technical requirements for logical preservation, ensuring that data remains authentic, interpretable, and accessible far into the future.

General observations on the maturity of long-term preservation policy and implementation

The group has not agreed on recommendations for specific infrastructures, as the requirements for long-term preservation remain insufficiently defined and not yet aligned across the universities. This is particularly

evident in the unclear division of responsibilities between local and national infrastructures. At present, only the National Archives hold a clearly defined mandate for long-term preservation.

Long-term preservation of FAIR research data depends on a range of supporting infrastructures, including catalogues for metadata formats, controlled vocabularies, and persistent identifier services. These components are clear candidates for shared national infrastructure, as they provide the common foundations needed for interoperability and consistent practice of the FAIR principles. These supporting infrastructures are just as important as the repositories themselves. DeIC Datasite is a national service for issuing DOI's, but other PID's are needed to integrate with EOSC. At the moment there seems to be a gap in the national FAIR policy regarding these supporting infrastructures.

Recommendation(s):

We recommend that the three preservation classes be adopted as a guiding framework for future planning of long-term preservation workflows and infrastructures.

We recommend that universities agree on where and when data should be transferred between local and national infrastructures within each of the three preservation classes. Such agreement is essential for developing sustainable national solutions for long-term preservation and for establishing coherent workflows that keep the practical burden on researchers low.

We are aware that several universities are currently working to strengthen their supporting infrastructures for research data management. While these initiatives rightly address the full lifecycle of research data, it would be beneficial if institutions coordinated their approaches to long-term preservation and considered common requirements to shared national infrastructures for long-term preservation. We recommend that universities try to agree on a common approach to long-term preservation.

We recommend establishing a national policy for the coordinated use of persistent identifiers. Such a policy should define the roles and use of key PID types, including the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD), which aligns well with the reporting requirements of the National Archives.

Appendices:

Focus area 5:

How can services for data management planning continue to be developed nationally and internationally, be made machine-readable, and be used in connection with the submission of research data to the National Archives?

Goal(s):

The purpose is to provide an overview of which DMP tools are actually used by Danish researchers, as well as to identify the key trends in the development of machine-actionable DMP tools (maDMP tools).

Reporting:

Study of the use of DMP tools

In 2025, the working group distributed the survey *Research Data Storage and Management at Danish Universities*. As responses were received from only three universities, the group assesses that the results do not yet provide a representative national picture. The survey will therefore be redistributed in early 2026, with a focus on increasing outreach to the universities that have not yet responded.

Key trends in the development of DMP tools

Machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) extend traditional digital DMPs by enabling actions to be carried out directly on the infrastructure services used by researchers. A central challenge is that an maDMP system must be able to perform administrative operations across multiple organisational and technical domains, which makes broad implementation complex.

This challenge is increasingly being addressed through workflow automation tools originally developed for data and computational workflows across HPC and cloud environments. Work is now underway to generate DMPs directly from workflow descriptions, ensuring that the data management plan reflects the actual process. In addition, there has been significant growth in experimentation with the use of LLMs for the automatic generation of both workflows and data management plans.

In 2026, the working group will continue to monitor developments both internationally and at Danish universities.

Recommendation(s):

Appendices:

Focus area 6

Elaborate on how research institutions work with security infrastructure (Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure, AAAI) specifically and especially for sensitive data, with the aim of also making these FAIR.

Goal(s):

The aim of this report is to give the reader an overview of the current state of AAAI in the Danish research infrastructure landscape and to describe how this relates to international developments. This provides the basis for recommendations on how Denmark can strengthen its approach to authentication, authorisation, and accounting and align with emerging European frameworks.

Reporting:

The AAAI acronym covers Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure. Authentication is a prerequisite for both authorisation and accounting, but it is essential to recognise that these are three distinct problem domains. Each is implemented through its own mechanisms, protocols, and components, following standards defined by different governing bodies.

Authentication is the infrastructure function that verifies who a user is and establishes a trusted digital identity. During authentication, the user logs in at an Identity Provider (IdP), which validates the user's credentials, applies any required multi-factor authentication, and determines whether the login meets the relevant assurance requirements. Protocol gateways (e.g., SAML or OIDC) package the outcome into a standardised login session containing information about the users affiliations and entitlements. All of these components operate within a broader federation framework for a given domain. In the research and education domain this ensures that services can rely on the identity information issued by the user's home institution.

Authorisation is the process that determines what an authenticated user is allowed to access. It is an integral part of the service the user is attempting to use. When a user requests access to the service or to a resource

within it, the service's access-control policies decide whether to grant or deny access based on the user's affiliations and entitlements. These affiliations and entitlements are obtained either from attributes delivered in the login session or retrieved from local directory and entitlement services.

Accounting records how authenticated and authorised users consume resources. It logs user activity and the amount of compute, storage, or other service capacity consumed. This usage information is then reported to the domain's resource-management system, which matches actual consumption against the resource grants issued within the domain (e.g., EuroHPC, EOSC, DeiC). In this way, accounting provides the basis for monitoring utilisation, ensuring fair allocation, and supporting reporting.

It is the combination of these separate infrastructure services handling authentication, authorisation, and accounting that together enable controlled and auditable access across a larger digital research infrastructure.

Authentication in the context of Danish research

Two authentication domains are relevant for identifying users of national services in the Danish research sector. First, the research and education community operates a global identity federation that provides digital identities for researchers and students, and in which all Danish universities participate. Second, the European Commission is establishing an EU-wide identity federation that issues digital identities to all EU citizens, and in which the Danish state participates.

REFEDS (the Research and Education FEDerations group) is the international coordination body for identity federations in the research and education sector. It maintains the global trust framework that enables cross-institutional authentication using open standards such as SAML and OIDC. Nationally, each federation is governed by its own operator (e.g., WAYF in Denmark). Internationally, coordination takes place through REFEDS, where the European research network community, particularly GÉANT, plays a central role.

eIDAS is the EU-wide identity framework that enables cross-border authentication for all EU citizens and residents. It establishes a common trust framework in which each Member State operates a nationally governed electronic identity scheme that can be used to access digital services across the Union. National eID providers authenticate users through a national identity solution (e.g. MitID in Denmark). WAYF also operates as a broker for the Danish eID, providing Danish research institutions and infrastructures with convenient and free access to the eIDAS federation.

There is significant coordination in the development of these federations at the European level, and both are actively exploring a future migration towards digital-wallet-based identity solutions. A digital wallet can be imagined as a smartphone app or web service that securely holds a user's verified digital identity and the credentials needed to access services. These developments aim to strengthen interoperability and security across Europe and to simplify how users authenticate to research services.

Authorisation in the context of Danish research

All national research infrastructures established through DeiC authorise users via the WAYF federation, allowing users to log in using the digital identity provided by their home institution. A significant number of other services directed at the research and education community also support login through WAYF. However, there remains a substantial set of services that still rely on their own local user-management systems, resulting in parallel identity silos with duplicated account administration.

Accounting in the context of Danish research

Researchers can apply for access to Danish national research infrastructures through DeiC's coordinated call processes. When a PI is granted resources on a service, the allocation must be communicated to the providing infrastructure and its usage must be accounted and reported.

At present, resource management is handled differently across the Danish research infrastructures. Three approaches are currently in use: a shared Nordic resource-management system known as Puhuri; a national resource-management service, the DeiC Integration Portal; and local resource management performed directly within individual services. This diversity reflects historical development and service-specific needs, but also creates challenges for coordination and cross-service reporting.

AAAI for European research infrastructure

Two major European research infrastructure frameworks are currently being implemented: EuroHPC, which provides federated high-performance computing resources across Europe, and EOSC, which aims to create a federated ecosystem of research data and services. Both frameworks require consistent approaches to trust, identity, authorisation, and accounting across national and institutional boundaries, and they increasingly define the reference models that national infrastructures are expected to align with.

Recommendations for Danish AAAI infrastructure

The working Group recommends that Danish research infrastructure adopt the standards and solutions for handling authentication, authorisation, and accounting developed in the EuroHPC and EOSC frameworks. Both of these frameworks develop common policies, technical profiles, and interoperability models for identity, access management, and resource accounting across European research infrastructures. Aligning with these emerging standards will strengthen cross-border collaboration, reduce national duplication of effort, and ensure that Danish infrastructures remain compatible with the wider European ecosystem as it evolves.

Suggested changes to the focus areas of working group B:

The members of Working Group B do not generally come from AAAI infrastructure backgrounds, apart from the chair, and the wider group therefore lacks the specialised expertise required to evaluate and guide strategy in this area. We therefore propose adjusting the focus area to concentrate on what data controllers and researchers require from infrastructures in order to achieve more seamless data-management practices. This is a better match for the group's competencies and backgrounds and has the potential to provide valuable insights into the requirements for trust in the Danish research infrastructure.

Proposal for changing focus Area 6:

How can controllers of data maintain their data-protection obligations while granting responsible use of data for research? How can infrastructure support this, and what is required to make the process trusted and seamless across digital research environments?

If this change is accepted, the group will address these questions in the context of specific data domains, as the answers will vary significantly across domains. Future work should therefore include periods where the working group concentrates on individual domains and engages with the relevant stakeholders and experts associated with each. By focusing on concrete data domains, the group also hopes to maintain the interest of, and actively engage, researchers who work directly with these types of data, ensuring that the group's insights remain grounded in real research practice.

Appendices

6. Working group C – Financial plan for FAIR data

Working Group C addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 7, 8 and 9.

Focus area 7

EU programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) require grant recipients to develop data management plans in connection with applications. To what extent can national research funding organizations benefit from following this practice?

Goal(s):

To identify the advantages and disadvantages of a scenario where funding agencies introduce a requirement for data management plans (DMPs) and to assess the interest in developing a shared DMP-template for funding agencies implementing such a requirement. The group plans to conduct a scenario assessment to shed light on these aspects.

Reporting:

Working Group C has developed a series of recommendations and proposals for government funding agencies regarding the implementation of the FAIR principles (see appendix: *Working Group C: Proposals for FAIR-related Practice for Government Funding Agencies*). The proposals are based on a scenario analysis in which the funding agencies have introduced a requirement for applicants to prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) as part of the application process.

The working group recommends, among other things, that government funding agencies establish a consistent practice that supports research institutions in promoting FAIR compliance. The recommendations include, for example, that requirements for DMPs should be based on the Ministry of Higher Education and Science's (UFM) current guidelines, and that agencies should be able to cover any extraordinary project-specific costs associated with the preparation and implementation of DMPs. Where in the application process a DMP should be submitted depends on balancing the DMP's importance for the project, the resources required to prepare it—including for unfunded applications—and the administrative resources involved. Therefore, DMP requirements should be integrated at relevant stages, from application submission to contract negotiations. The group finds that there will naturally be differences between typical smaller research projects and larger centers or data-driven projects (see Focus Area 9). Furthermore, it is emphasised that funding agencies should primarily ensure clear frameworks for requirements, timelines, and documentation, as well as contribute to national overviews of DMPs to enhance transparency and accessibility of research data.

In addition, the working group recommends that private funding agencies follow the same guidelines to ensure consistency, simplifying the application processes for researchers and facilitating FAIR implementation, while compliance and enforcement take place within research institutions according to UFM guidelines. Likewise, UFM/UFS may consider adjusting or updating their provisions and requirements for recipients of government research funding in relevant grant conditions and calls. Finally, research institutions could consider establishing procedures for assessing the quality and content of DMPs in accordance with applicable disciplinary standards in the research field

Recommendation(s):

The working group's recommendations can be found in the appendix: *Working Group C: Proposals for FAIR-related Practice for Government Funding Agencies*.

Appendices:

- [Forslag til praksis vedrørende FAIR for statslige fonde](#)
- [Fondskrav til Data Management: En case sammenligning mellem Danmarks Grundforskningsfond \(DG\) og Innovationsfonden](#)

Focus area 8

How can we ensure that research data and other electronic objects underlying published research results are stored in accordance with FAIR principles after the project ends, including at minimum a Persistent Identifier (PID) and publicly available metadata, even if the data is not openly accessible?

Goal(s):

The original goal has changed during the process and is now included in Focus Area 9 (see below).

Reporting:

The focus area has been interpreted as relating to the practices of funding bodies and research institutions concerning the storage of data after the completion of grant-funded projects. The group's work has shown that this question is closely linked to Focus Area 9, which clarifies which data-management costs may be included in project budgets; therefore, the group has addressed focus areas 8 and 9 together. On this basis, the group has prepared a proposed formulation, which appears in the recommendations under Focus Area 9 and is reproduced below.

It is emphasised that not all data must necessarily be preserved after a project ends. The decision on how long and to what extent data should be stored should be made by the individual research institution. This assessment should be based on scholarly, legal, and ethical considerations, as well as on the research relevance of the data and their potential for future use.

Recommendation(s):

Based on the scholarly assessment of the value of the data and the applicable regulations (including disciplinary and legal requirements), it is recommended that costs for long-term preservation be included in the proposed budget at the time of application.

Appendices:**Focus area 9**

What costs related to data management can be included in budgets?

Goal(s):

The working group recommends continued dialogue between universities and funding agencies regarding the lack of visibility of data management costs in budgets and financial reports. The group will explore how to best communicate its conclusions to relevant stakeholders.

Reporting:

The group initially worked toward the objective of developing recommendations that could contribute to a more detailed specification of data-management costs for the dialogue between Danish Universities and the funding bodies.

The group took as its point of departure the agreement between the universities and the six private foundations on the financing of research projects from summer 2024⁵. This agreement clarifies that expenses related to IT infrastructure—including access to computers, data storage, software, licences, and other related resources available to all researchers—cannot be requested as a separate budget line in applications. At the same time, the agreement states that *“in cases of extraordinary needs for storage or computational power, possibly through a core facility, such costs may be budgeted (the need must be justified).”* Based on the working group’s experience, Danish funding bodies—both public and private—generally follow this practice and finance relevant data-management costs not covered by project supplements or overhead, provided that these costs are clearly justified in the application. The relationship between the project activities and the budget items forms part of the evaluation process. It is therefore not uncommon for data management to be included under *Dissemination* activities.

Good data-management practices—including record-keeping, data structuring, and curation for the purpose of sharing and publication—is an integral part of good research practice and thus an implicitly approved activity in all research projects. The need for resources for data management varies across research fields, and the group has therefore divided needs into three user groups. It is assessed that separate budgeting is only necessary for extraordinarily large projects—for example, major cohort studies, the establishment of databases, non-reproducible observational studies (e.g., election data, climate data), or experiments with high costs or ethical considerations (such as animal experiments) that should not be repeated.

Data volumes and research data–management needs

1. **Standard users** with relatively modest data-management needs

Standard users typically require only a few terabytes of storage and handle data management as an integrated part of their daily work—for example, through a (laboratory) notebook system, local/national data storage, and publication workflows. A study at the University of Copenhagen shows that the vast majority (>99%) of the university’s users fall into this category, meaning that explicit budgeting for data storage and management will only be relevant in a small number of cases.

2. **Users with larger needs** that can be handled locally

Some users require more storage capacity, the handling of GDPR-regulated data, special security measures, and staff with data-management responsibilities, but where the data can still be managed locally within the universities. This group primarily consists of researchers in the natural sciences, social sciences, and health sciences, who know their needs and normally budget for these expenses. As described in the agreement on project supplements, costs such as long-term storage (up to 10 years) and support from a data scientist may be included explicitly in the project budget. Since the curation period often extends beyond the project period (typically up to 5 years), it is recommended that total curation costs are calculated and settled during the project period, while universities locally handle the pre-financing.

3. **Users with extraordinary needs** that require, for example, specialised infrastructure

Users with exceptionally large data-management requirements include researchers affiliated with major national or international research facilities such as CERN, ESO, ESA, NASA, and databases for protein structures or gene sequences. In these environments, costs and processes for data curation are already embedded in the facilities and managed at the national or international level. It is

⁵ [Agreement on a joint model for research project funding](#)

therefore considered difficult to develop general models to cover data-management costs for individual projects in this category.

Costs for data management for user group 1 should already be covered within the project, overhead, or the project supplement. For Group 2, extraordinary data-management expenses are included in the application, while ordinary expenses are covered by the project and its supplement. An approved pricing structure is necessary: as a concrete example, one can refer to the full-cost calculation of data storage that the University of Copenhagen commissioned from the consultancy firm Deloitte. Here, the 2025 price is 980 DKK per TB per year (hot storage with full backup and disaster recovery). Thus, the cost of storing 20 TB of data for 10 years would need to be budgeted at a total of 196,000 DKK. (The price is indicative, and cold storage is expected to be roughly half that amount.) Group 3 is not included in this assessment due to its complexity. A standard should be developed for one-time settlement of costs for data preservation that extends beyond the project period.

Recommendation(s):

- The standard expenses for data management are already included in the agreement between the universities and the foundations in order to minimise administrative costs, for example through overhead (public foundations) and project supplements (private foundations). This should be reviewed regularly, for example when these agreements are updated. Mapping shows that the average researcher across disciplines has relatively manageable data-management expenses.
- Enhanced data-management policies are being implemented at the individual universities. The working group recommends that universities ensure that curation and similar tasks are carried out in accordance with current policies. The foundations do not have the resources for this task.
- It is recommended that universities prepare an overview including unit prices for common major data-management expenses related to extraordinary large-scale data-management tasks, such as data storage and salary costs for data managers. A small minority of researchers have extraordinary data-management expenses. These should be described and estimated in the application.
- The foundations should consider mentioning “data-management expenses” directly in the application guidelines for calls where a significant number of applications with such needs are expected⁶.
- Based on the scientific assessment of the value of the data and the applicable regulations (disciplinary and legal requirements), it is recommended that long-term preservation costs be included in the requested budget at the time of application.

Appendices:

⁶ Based on a sample from the following foundations—Novo Nordisk Foundation, Villum Foundation, Carlsberg Foundation, and Lundbeck Foundation—data-management expenses are mentioned specifically for infrastructure and data-science programs, for example [Villum Infrastructure](#), [NNF Large Equipment and Facilities](#), and [NNF Data Science Emerging Investigator](#).

7. Working group D- Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

Working Group D addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 10, 11, 12, and 13. The group has categorised the focus areas and related actions into three topics: (1) Data Stewardship, (2) National Competence Center, and (3) Recognition and Rewarding regarding FAIR Data Management

(D1) Data Stewardship

Focus area 10

(D1) What competence profiles have research institutions established for the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers? How have research institutions built the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers?

Goal(s):

- Mapping the organisational Data Stewardship landscape in Denmark
- Mapping the Data Stewardship competence landscape in Denmark

Reporting:

In 2025, Working Group D completed a comprehensive national survey of staff who provide data stewardship support at Danish universities. This marks an important milestone, as it is the first systematic mapping of who is doing data stewardship, how they are organised, and what kinds of support they provide. The survey gathered 101 responses. Of these, 75 participants answered most questions, and 36 completed the full survey. Although these numbers are relatively limited, we consider the responses to provide a broadly representative picture of data stewardship support at Danish universities. The results reveal a diverse and evolving data stewardship landscape. Most respondents report that they spend the largest share of their working time on core activities such as data management planning and data management infrastructure, followed by activities in training, outreach, research advice, data analysis, legal issues, and tool-specific support. While researchers are the primary recipients of support activities, technical-administrative staff and students also benefit significantly.

The survey also highlights skills gaps and training needs. Respondents prioritise competence development in data management planning and infrastructure, followed by data reuse and data publication. In other words, the same areas that professionals report spending most of their working time on are also where they feel the strongest need for upskilling. This is a clear signal that the professionalisation of the field is still underway.

Finally, in terms of organisation, data stewardship is spread across central units, cross-faculty teams, and faculty or department-level support. This indicates the prevalence of a mixed model that combines specialised central support units with individual embedded data stewards, reflecting a flexible approach to organising data stewardship support rather than a single standardised role. Professional backgrounds and job titles confirm this diversity: data stewardship in Denmark is delivered by researchers, technical-administrative employees, and explicitly labelled “data steward” or “data manager” profiles.

Looking back, the survey provides a first national picture of how the field has developed since 2015, when Denmark introduced its first National Strategy for Research Data Management. Most respondents have worked with data stewardship for less than five years, with a smaller group reporting 5 to 10 years of

experience and only a few with more than a decade. Those who identify as data stewards or data managers typically work full-time on data stewardship tasks, while researchers and many technical-administrative employees contribute on a part-time or ad hoc basis. This pattern suggests that the most significant growth in capacity has occurred in the past five to ten years, accelerating after the publication of the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR Principles in September 2021.

Lastly, Working Group D has begun to characterise distinct configurations of data stewardship support: full-time versus ad hoc roles, central versus embedded support functions, and combinations of researchers, technical-administrative employees, and dedicated data stewards. This work lays the foundation for a more consolidated description of the Danish data stewardship landscape that can inform future recommendations on staffing and competence development.

In 2026, we will complement the survey results and our analysis with focus groups and semi-structured interviews with selected respondent groups. Combining these qualitative insights with the existing survey data will enable us to move beyond descriptive mapping and deliver concrete, evidence-based recommendations for how institutions can staff and organise their data stewardship support functions. In parallel, we will align the identified professional profiles and skills gaps with European skills frameworks to pinpoint where national coordination or shared offerings, such as training programmes and communities of practice, could complement local initiatives and strengthen capacity across institutions.

Recommendation(s):

Working Group D recommends continuing and expanding this work in 2026, with a view to supporting the professionalisation and consolidation of data stewardship in Denmark.

Appendices:

(D2) National Competence center

Focus area 11

To what extent is there interest in developing and offering the research support function collectively at the national level? For example, under a central or decentralized national competence center.

Focus area 12

Is there interest among research institutions in national coordination of educational offerings (not research support) within FAIR research data management? Can a potential national collaboration aim at division of labor, specialisation, and joint national offerings of educational programs, such as through a competence center under the auspices of DeIC? This includes education at all levels, from bachelor to further education of scientific staff.

Goal(s):

- Presentation of organisational models of a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management,
- Presentation of potential services of a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management,
- Overview of institutional needs and interests in relation to creating a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management in Denmark,
- Overview of institutional needs and interests regarding national coordination of FAIR Data Management education and training in Denmark.

Reporting:

In 2025, Working Group D advanced its work on organisational models for a potential National Competence Center (NCC) for FAIR data management and stewardship. We consolidated and extended international case studies started in 2024, drawing on examples from Finland, the Netherlands, Germany, the UK, Austria, France, and Italy. This resulted in a structured overview of how existing NCCs organise governance, funding, and service portfolios.

Using Mintzberg's (1983) organisational typology as an analytical lens, we identified four main approaches: centralised and standardised organisations such as JISC; expert-driven models like CSC, DANS, and UK DCC; federated or member-based structures such as SURF, NFDI, and Recherche Data Gouv; and agile, project-based organisations exemplified by the Netherlands eScience Center. This typology clarifies the trade-offs between stability and flexibility, and between national alignment and local responsiveness that a Danish NCC would need to navigate.

International mapping also shows convergence on core services: developing and disseminating national guidance and best practices aligned with EOSC; coordinating and delivering training for different audiences; supporting domain and cross-domain communities of practice; providing expert consultancy on data stewardship and infrastructure planning; and, in some cases, managing parts of the national research data infrastructure such as repositories and metadata services.

On the basis of the international comparison, we are currently discussing scenarios for a Danish NCC that combine different configurations of governance structure, funding model, service portfolio, and typical staff profiles. These scenarios are designed as tools for structured stakeholder consultations, not as ready-made blueprints.

Progress on institutional needs has been more preliminary. While the D.1 survey included questions on professional development and national coordination of training, it did not yield conclusive insights. Similarly, a workshop co-organised with Working Group A at the DeIC Conference 2025 provided valuable qualitative input on organising FAIR support and dividing responsibilities across local, national, and international levels. However, it did not produce systematic or representative data.

Overall, the goals of presenting organisational models and potential services have largely been achieved. By contrast, mapping institutional needs and interests remains incomplete, leaving Working Group D unable to recommend a mandate or a specific organisational model for a Danish NCC at this stage.

Reference

Mintzberg, H. (1983). *Structure in fives: Designing effective organizations*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.

Recommendation(s):

Working Group D recommends continuing and expanding this work in 2026, shifting from conceptual model-building to structured consultation with Danish research institutions.

Concretely, we propose to:

- Use the outlined NCC profiles as discussion tools in a targeted needs assessment involving institutional leadership, research support units, and data stewards.
- Design focus groups and interviews to clarify whether a Danish NCC is desirable, whether any service functions meaningfully could be centralised at the national level or should remain local, and whether national coordination of FAIR/RDM education and training may be a suitable alternative to current practice.
- Map opportunities for national coordination, such as shared training programmes and communities of practice, to complement local initiatives and strengthen capacity.

The outcome will be a set of evidence-based options, including governance and funding implications, to inform future decisions on whether to establish an NCC and whether to organise national coordination of FAIR data stewardship education and training in Denmark.

Appendices:

(D3) Recognition and Rewarding regarding FAIR Data Management

Focus area 13

How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally for FAIR data management practices at research institutions?

Goal(s):

- Overview of national or international recommendations on how to reward FAIR Data Management practices,
- Mapping current incentive structures for FAIR Data Management practices at Danish universities,
- Mapping current incentive structures for FAIR Data Management practices at international universities.

Reporting:

In 2024, Working Group D mapped key recommendations and initiatives on rewarding Open Science and FAIR data management, including DORA, CoARA, EU Council conclusions, ALLEA, the Barcelona Declaration, and various national and institutional award schemes. In 2025, the focus shifted from landscaping to operationalisation: how these principles can be translated into practical tools for assessment processes at Danish research institutions.

The main activity in 2025 was a joint workshop at the DeIC Conference 2025, “The Danish National FAIR Strategy: Cultural Change: Research Support and Research Assessment in the FAIR Era,” co-organised with Working Group A. One session addressed recognising and rewarding FAIR research outputs in hiring and promotion. Participants discussed practical prototype tools: policy text snippets defining which FAIR outputs like datasets, software, workflows, or protocols may be recognised and rewarded and under what conditions; a simple minimum FAIR eligibility bar for different outputs with clear red lines (e.g., no PID, no reuse terms); and brief checklists with a qualitative assessment rubric for applicants and reviewers. These prototypes are not formal recommendations but represent a first step toward practical tools that can be adapted locally.

The broader mapping goals under D.3 are therefore only partly addressed at this stage. The recommendations and award schemes identified in 2024 still form our main evidence base. The D.1 data stewardship survey offers some additional insight into incentives and recognition practices at Danish universities, but it was not designed as a dedicated D.3 instrument. A systematic mapping of how FAIR practices are rewarded is therefore planned for 2026. Until it is completed, Working Group D is not in a position to provide a comprehensive description of current institutional incentive structures or to propose concrete national reward schemes.

Recommendation(s):

Working Group D recommends that the work under D.3 in 2026 focuses on this systematic mapping of institutional incentive structures and on refining the tools developed at the DeiC workshop. More specifically, we propose to:

- Conduct structured interviews with relevant stakeholders to clarify where and how FAIR outputs are currently recognised at Danish research institutions.
- Refine the tools developed at the DeiC workshop (policy snippets, minimum FAIR eligibility bar, checklists, and rubric) through community co-creation. Where feasible, pilot these tools in a limited number of hiring, promotion, or award processes at Danish universities to assess their usefulness.
- Align this work with national efforts by collaborating with the emerging Danish CoARA national chapter, so that FAIR-sensitive assessment tools are developed and tested as part of broader reform efforts rather than in isolation.

These steps will allow Working Group D to move from prototypes and international examples toward evidence-based options for recognising and rewarding FAIR data management practices in Denmark.

Appendices:

8. Working group E – Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration

Working Group E addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 14, 15, and 16. The working group has renumbered the focus areas from the mandate so that focus area 14 is now 15, 15 is now 16, and 16 is now 14.

Focus area 14 – data sensitivity

Can a better understanding be provided for the spectrum of data sensitivity? That is to say, not only personal sensitivity but also agreements, dual-use pre-prints, IPR, etc., including the researchers' own criteria for how the sensitivity of their data can be understood.

Goal(s):

Mapping URIS experiences, as well as general experiences from work related to the implementation of other security measures.

Reporting:

Based on the government's [URIS guidelines](#) (*Committee on Guidelines for International Research and Innovation Collaboration*), which to some extent engage with related questions and issues within the focus area—for example Dual Use and IPR (*intellectual property rights*) in relation to Europe's security and competitiveness—the working group has contacted all universities and obtained responses from most of the universities' URIS coordinators. The inquiry asked for experiences regarding data sensitivity, general experiences related to the implementation of URIS, and other security measures at the universities in connection with critical research and sensitive data.

The practical implementation of the URIS guidelines—in the form of measures and completed activities—varies across the universities, and the need for such measures depends on the respective institutions' research areas and external collaborations.

However, based on the feedback received, the following can be summarised:

- Based on the feedback, it is clear that there is no single, unambiguous definition of data sensitivity. The experiences from the CISO Forum regarding uniform data classification across the universities confirm that, among other things due to the institutions' differing levels of maturity in terms of measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data, it is very difficult to achieve a common understanding and definition of data sensitivity.
- Systematic mapping of critical research is carried out to a large extent at the department level. This mapping is conducted, for example, annually with the involvement of the departments. The results contribute to a more nuanced understanding of data sensitivity and provide a knowledge base for risk assessment, mitigating measures, governance, and dialogue with researchers.
- Formulation of:
 - o A) Risk profiles for the departments and assessments of how these are maintained. For example, data mining is conducted from the TIM database (EU)⁷ using publication data, which forms the basis for a risk profile.

⁷ <https://data.europa.eu/en/publications/use-cases/tim-open-access>

- B) Risk assessments, where it is evaluated that the greatest risk of “undesired knowledge transfer” in a general sense relates to situations in which employees, part-time staff, visitors, and students do not have the necessary knowledge or tools to counter the risk of “undesired knowledge transfer.”
- Emphasis is placed on the criteria in PET’s Assessment of the Espionage Threat Against Denmark, the Faroe Islands, and Greenland (May 2023), as well as on research in selected technology areas covered by the EU’s recommendation on critical technologies (Regulation (EU) 2024/795 Establishing the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP)⁸.
- At some universities, an overarching strategy based on a risk-based approach is used in an effort to preserve academic freedom while also implementing necessary security measures.
- Experience shows that it is essential to integrate URIS initiatives into existing processes and to support a culture in which researchers are equipped to identify and manage risks, for example through self-assessments for research involving export control, dual-use, or commercial potential, and through decisions to avoid collaboration with certain universities with military ties.
- Implementation of “physical security,” which includes access control and CCTV monitoring of areas with “critical research,” as well as various measures related to international collaborative projects, guest access, and travel security, all of which may affect data sharing. For example, “clean laptops” are offered for travel to high-risk countries, and background checks are conducted for critical research activities. At the same time, active efforts are made to avoid unintentional discrimination and ensure that all measures are based on objective assessments.

Recommendation(s):

Appendices:

Indsatsområde 15 – Relevant security requirements
What are the security requirements in connection with the sharing of data?

Goal(s):

Contributing to the work in working groups A, B, and F.

Reporting:

The working group has prepared a document⁹ outlining a set of broad principles for handling security aspects that should be incorporated into the continued work on the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles.

This section provides a summary of the main points from that document, which can be found as an appendix to this recommendation. The appendix elaborates on the key principles and points of attention regarding security in connection with data sharing, including technical, organisational, and legal considerations.

Security requirements for data sharing should always be adapted to the type of data and its classification. Particularly sensitive or confidential data require stronger protection and should be managed through

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/strategic-technologies-for-europe-platform-step.html>

⁹ See appendix: Working Group E – Overall principles regarding safety aspects in relation to the National Strategy for Data Management based on FAIR

appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as access control (e.g., MFA), role-based access, encryption, and activity logging. In addition, institutions are encouraged to work systematically with risk assessment, operations and incident management, backup, vendor management, and awareness and training, in accordance with the ISO 27001/2 standards¹⁰.

Anonymisation and pseudonymisation should be applied wherever possible to reduce the risk of identification. This can be achieved, for example, through techniques such as *k-anonymity*, *differential privacy*, or *synthetic data*.

Recommendation(s):

Since the universities have different data classification models and levels of maturity, it is not possible to establish shared **detailed** requirements across institutions. However, the working group recommends developing a common model for data classification that can support uniform security standards.

As an example, and as basic guidance, the following classification model can be used:

Level	Example of data	Protection focus	Measures
0: Public data	Published research results	Availability	Standard security protocols
1: Internal data	Raw data, internal documents	Integrity and availability	+ RBAC, secure networks, MFA
2: Confidential data	Personal data, trade secrets	Confidentiality and integrity	+ Pseudonymisation, encryption, logging
3: Critical data	Special categories of personal data, societally critical data	Confidentiality, protection against misuse	+ Anonymization, geographic restrictions, physical security, penetration tests

The CISO Forum under Universities Denmark can be involved to help refine the principles and provide advice on security-related matters.

Appendices:

- [Overordnede principper i forhold til sikkerhedsaspekter i relation til National strategi for data-management baseret på FAIR](#)

Indsatsområde 16 – approved solutions/services

In light of research groups' needs to work nationally and internationally with sensitive data, which requires strong and flexible governance, elaborate on the national and international solutions/services that can support this need.

Goal(s):

Assessment of universities' maturity in processes supporting vendor approval.

¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

Reporting:

The working group assesses that, at this stage, it is not possible to provide a clear answer as to which national and international solutions or services can support the needs of research groups working with sensitive data. This is primarily due to the fact that the area is highly dependent on organisational context. The individual universities operate with different data classification models and security measures, making it difficult to evaluate and describe in general terms whether a given system or service can be considered suitable for handling sensitive data.

Furthermore, there is a lack of alignment between the current wording of the focus area and the practical processes applied by the universities. In practice, issues related to data security, classification, and risk assessment are handled differently, and a common framework for evaluating suitable solutions has not yet been established.

Recommendation(s):

The necessary prerequisites for answering the questions in the focus area are currently being developed within the CISO Forum under Universities Denmark. The forum is working to establish a common understanding and model for data classification and security principles, which may eventually form the basis for a more uniform assessment of solutions and services. When and if material on this is developed, it will be shared with the other working groups for possible integration into their areas.

Appendices:

9. Working group F – Valuation of Data

Working Group F addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus area 17.

Focus area 17

What criteria for a dynamic value of data - as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context- are applied by local, national, and international organisations to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

Goal(s):

To ensure alignment between ambition and available resources, Working Group F has categorised its' goals as primary and secondary. Secondary goals maintain equal importance but may need to be partially deferred to 2026.

Introduction

Throughout 2025, Working Group F has continued its mandate to investigate, articulate, and operationalise the concept of data value within and across the Danish Universities. Compared to the strong momentum achieved during 2024, the pace of work in 2025 was reduced as workgroup members have had to prioritise significant local initiatives. This challenge affected most working groups under the Reference Group and, for Working Group F, limited the available time for coordination, data collection, and interviews.

Despite this reduced pace, Working Group F advanced key elements of its task: preparing the foundation for a national framework for data valuation, expanding national and international knowledge collection, and refining methods for stakeholder engagement. The work in 2025 builds directly on the foundational deliverables from 2024, as published in the Annual Report 2024 – National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14615125), and follows the goals articulated in the Goals and Action Plan for the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR Principles – 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15281348).

This report builds upon the above documents and summarises activities conducted in 2025; assesses progress on primary and secondary goals as defined in the Action Plan; provides an overview of accomplishments and necessary postponements; and outlines next steps for 2026.

Mandate and Focus Area

Working Group F addresses Focus Area 17 under the National Strategy for Data Management:

What criteria for a dynamic value of data—as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context—are applied by local, national, and international organisations to assess preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability?

As established in 2024, the focus area extends beyond storage providers and encompasses the entire research data lifecycle, the diversity of stakeholders influencing data decisions, and the interplay between societal, scientific, economic, replacement, and compliance dimensions of value. This interpretation remains central in 2025.

Summary of Accomplishments

Working Group F achieved the following results:

- Conducted a coordinated national literature review, including international scanning.
- Strengthened the conceptual understanding of data value within research data management practice at Danish universities.
- Developed legal and procedural foundations for stakeholder interviews.
- Presented the work internationally at International Data Week 2025 and collected input on related international activities.
- Refined and expanded the data value framework building blocks.
- Increased alignment with Working Groups C, D, and E through individual meetings and the March seminar.
- Prepared groundwork for a concluding deliverable expected in 2026.

These accomplishments contribute significantly to the national understanding of data value and prepare the environment for full data collection and reporting in 2026.

Activities deferred to 2026

The following key activities will be carried into 2026:

- Publication of Zotero library – pending final Q/A and integration of late-year sources.
- Execution of full stakeholder interview series – pending legal and institutional approvals.
- Publication of the first framework version on Zenodo – pending input from the series of interview.
- Report analysing how data value informs university practice – dependent on the above.
- Minor goal: development of metrics for framework adoption – dependent on the above.

The reasons for deferrals are consistent across tasks: resource limitations, institutional focus on local initiatives, GDPR compliance and data governance processes that are prerequisites for our data collection, and the interdependence of Working Group F's goals.

Reporting:

The 2025 work unfolded across a series of planned meetings, workshops, interviews, and international engagements. Despite a slower pace from the previous year, the group maintained a regular meeting cadence and delivered several significant milestones. A substantial part of this slowdown stemmed from ensuring full compliance with the legal framework for gathering and collaborating on personally identifiable information under GDPR, as this required members to consult legal advisers within their respective institutions before interviews and data collection could proceed.

The year began with a focus on literature work and methodological alignment. In January, the group convened for a full-day workshop for the first phase of the rapid literature review and refinement of the structure of the shared Zotero environment. The purpose of the review was to identify already existing literature, initiatives and expertise that could help us draft a first version of a framework for the value of research data, including different value types and factors that can affect value.

During February and early March, the group took part in joint activities with the other working groups under the FAIR Reference Group, including the cross-group seminar in Odense. These meetings sharpened the understanding of overlaps—particularly with Working Groups C and E—and highlighted the importance of integrating perspectives from information security, long-term preservation, and policy development. The internal workshop held shortly thereafter allowed the group to consolidate these insights and adjust its internal plan for the remainder of the year. In this workshop the group started identifying interviewees and doing preparatory work for interviews. The purpose of the interviews is to qualify the first version of the data value framework, by asking stakeholder perspectives on why data value assessments are relevant and how

they assess value, among others. The preparatory workshop brought forward a clearer view of the institutional landscape, including the distinct roles of researchers, information security officers, research support staff, funders, and archival institutions. It also marked the first full discussion of the legal foundation required for data collection, including consent documents, joint data controller agreements, and local registration procedures.

As expected, the summer schedules slowed progress, but the groundwork laid earlier in the year enabled the group to test the emerging interview guide in both June and August, by conducting two pilot interviews with two university representatives. In this period, the drafting of the legal foundations was also being processed at the individual institutions of the group members.

August and September were shaped by the representation of the group by Susanne den Boer Beckers at International Data Week 2025 in Brisbane. In this presentation, Susanne presented the present version of the framework for data value and was able to collect input on factors that set value to data. She furthermore identified related international initiatives, as well as international experts that are willing to be interviewed by the group in 2026. The presentation sparked interest among international peers and the experiences both broadened the group's horizon and enriched the ongoing literature and landscape review.

In November, the group reconvened for an extended meeting that served as a capstone for the year preparing for the yearly report and planning for the coming year.

Progress on Goals and Actions

The Goals and Action Plan for 2025 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15281348) identifies six goals, split up into primary goals (A–C) to complete first and secondary goals (D–F) that are dependent of the primary goals. Activities in 2025 will be assessed against this structure. A revised action plan will be published in the spring of 2026.

Primary Goals

- **Goal A: Publish a common Zotero reference library**

Status: Nearly completed

The group consolidated literature from the rapid review, NotebookLM-assisted screenings, and international reports. Zotero folder structures were refined; tagging conventions established; and initial quality assurance performed. Still, time constraints and institutional workloads delayed final consolidation and validation. Also, several interesting literature sources emerged during International Data Week presentation, which will add to the value of this library.

- **Goal B: Develop and publish a foundational framework for data value**

Status: Substantial progress

The framework—grounded in the 2024 version—was refined through workshops, pilot interviews, literature findings and feedback from the conference. Building blocks, value categories, prerequisites, and stakeholder roles were revisited with practical examples. A draft nearing readiness for external review exists.

- **Goal C: Establish a process for framework updates and maintenance**

Status: Awaits completion of the publication of the first framework version.

Secondary Goals

Secondary goals are recognised as equally important but expected from the outset to extend into 2026.

- **Goal D: Conduct stakeholder interviews**

Status: On schedule for 2026

Completed two pilot interviews adding valuable information to both the interview guide and the Framework. Approval of legal processes for collaboration agreement, joint data controller agreement and GDPR compliance are in progress.

- **Goal E: Produce a report analysing how data valuation informs university data management processes and how stakeholders envision the proposed framework adding value to these processes.**

Status: Scheduled for 2026

Substantial theoretical groundwork established (framework building blocks, interview thematic structure). Initial insights gathered from the pilot interviews and cross-group seminar in March.

- **Goal F: Explore metrics for framework adoption**

Status: Planned for 2026

Metrics depend on both the completed framework and stakeholder response data. Working Group F explicitly scheduled this as the final goal due to sequencing dependencies.

Conclusion

Working Group F made steady progress in developing a national understanding of data value and preparing the foundation for comprehensive stakeholder engagement. The work carried out this year positions the group to complete the core goals of the mandate in 2026, with a strong basis in literature, international alignment, and early stakeholder insights.

The value of data remains a complex, dynamic, and context-dependent phenomenon. The 2025 work affirms the need for continued national coordination and sustained effort—guided by the FAIR principles and informed by real-world practices across Danish research institutions.

Appendices:

10. Implementing the strategy in an international context

The Danish national strategy for research data management based on the FAIR principles, was initiated in response to growing international expectations for responsible and interoperable data sharing. The global

FAIR movement, the EU's Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive (now the Open Data Directive), and the continuous development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) highlighted the need for Denmark to align with international frameworks to ensure a standard adoption of the FAIR principles in Denmark.

As part of this effort, the DeIC Board approved the establishment of DeIC Dataverse, a national repository based on the internationally developed open-source Dataverse software led by Harvard University's IQSS. Once the legal and governance requirements are in place, the service will provide a national, standards-based infrastructure that supports FAIR data management. This aligns Denmark with a growing international community of Dataverse adopters and its active global consortium, helping ensure that national practices remain harmonised with evolving international standards for research infrastructures and services.

Internationally, the realisation of FAIR principles depends fundamentally on agreements of standards. Conventions for metadata, persistent identifiers, controlled vocabularies, and data formats ensure that information retains its shared meaning across systems, disciplines, and borders. Organisations such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA), ISO, W3C, Knowledge Exchange, and EOSC projects play key roles in shaping these standards, which are becoming increasingly essential as research becomes more automated, data-intensive, and globally interconnected.

Standardisation is equally crucial for security and trustworthiness. Common frameworks for authentication, authorisation, data integrity, and repository certification create a coherent and predictable security environment. Authentication, authorization, and accounting infrastructure (AAAI) and Federated Identity Management systems, such as the Danish WAYF (Where Are You From) demonstrate how standardised authentication protocols provide secure, reliable access to research services across institutions, reducing vulnerabilities and supporting seamless collaboration.

EOSC illustrates how a standards-driven approach can scale across countries and infrastructures. Its shared metadata schemas, persistent identifier frameworks, and certification guidelines enable national services—such as DeIC Dataverse—to interoperate within a broader federated European environment. For Denmark, participation in EOSC strengthens national capabilities while ensuring that Danish research data remains discoverable, reusable, and secure.

11. Overview of the FAIR Reference group and working groups

This report was prepared by working groups established by the FAIR Reference group, at the mandate of The Ministry of Higher Education and Science.

FAIR Reference group

- Helle Zinner Henriksen, Copenhagen Business School (**Chair**, from september 2025)
- John Renner Hansen, University of Copenhagen, DeIC (Until june 2025)
- Annemarie Falktoft, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Anne Sofie Fink, DeIC
- Lasse Aistrup Rosendahl, Aarhus University
- Børge Lindberg, Innovation Fund Denmark
- Morten Andreasen, Danish National Research Foundation
- Lene Oddershede, Novo Nordisk Foundation
- Ulla Gro Nielsen, Novo Nordisk Foundation
- Carsten Sørensen, Copenhagen Business School
- Emilie Dupont Skovgaard, Universities Denmark
- Kim Brinckmann, University of Copenhagen
- Martin Svensson, University of Southern Denmark
- Søren Broberg Nielsen, Aarhus University
- Hanne-Louise Kirkegaard, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Tore Burkal Larsen, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- Kasper Ørum Køhler Simonsen, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- René Belsø, DeIC (Specialist secretarial support)
- Sandra Boerman, DeIC (Specialist secretarial support)

Working group A – Policies, tools and research support for FAIR data management

- Kirsten Krogh Kruuse, Royal Danish Library (Chair)
- Bjørn Høj Jakobsen, University of Southern Denmark
- Ding He, Technical University of Denmark
- Jens Grønbech Hansen, Aarhus University
- Jens Hybschmann, IT University of Copenhagen
- Konstantinos Tsirigos, Technical University of Denmark (Until may 2025)
- Lars Ove Dragsted, University of Copenhagen (Until january 2025)
- Kristoffer Gulmark Poulsen, Copenhagen Business School
- Siri Volker, University of Copenhagen
- René, Belsø, DeIC

Working group B – Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation

- Bo Bai, DeIC (Chair)
- Jonas Rank Møller, University of Copenhagen
- Julian Quick, Technical University of Denmark
- Tjerk Heijboer, GEUS
- Asger Væring Larsen, Royal Danish Library
- Hans Henrik Halvbjørn, Danish National Archives
- Nicolaj Pedersen Tanderup, DeIC

Working Group C – Financial plan for FAIR data

- Ulla Gro Nielsen, Novo Nordisk Foundation (Chair)
- Ulrik Nicolaj de Lichtenberg, Novo Nordisk Foundation (Until March 2025)
- Lise Arleth, University of Copenhagen
- Jakob Sørensen, Aarhus University
- Birger Larsen, Aalborg University (Until September 2025)
- John Renner Hansen, University of Copenhagen, DeIC (Until June 2025)
- Tore Burkal Larsen, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- Kasper Ørum Køhler Simonsen, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- Børge Lindberg, Innovationsfonden
- Morten Andreasen, Danmarks Grundforskningsfond
- Ole Kæseler Andersen, Aalborg University
- Sandra Boerman, DeIC

Working Group D – Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

- Mareike Buss, Copenhagen Business School (Chair)
- Haakon Lund, University of Copenhagen
- Sara Marie Westh, Aarhus University
- Evgenios Vlachos, University of Southern Denmark
- Claus Hansen, Aalborg University
- Falco Hüser, Royal Danish Library
- Sacha Zurcher, Royal Danish Library
- Hannah Mihai, DeIC

Working group E – Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration

- Thomas Schlicting, University of Copenhagen (Chair)
- Peter Severin de Fønss, Aarhus University
- Robert Smith, Aalborg University
- Mads Sinkjær Kjærgaard, Roskilde University
- Bjørn Høj Jakobsen, University of Southern Denmark
- Janni Lee Brodersen, University of Southern Denmark
- Lasse Tougaard Friis, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Jakob Bech Petersen, DeIC
- Morten Als Pedersen, DeIC

Working Group F – Valuation of data

- Per Møldrup-Dalum, Aarhus University (Chair)
- Susanne den Boer Beckers, University of Copenhagen
- Søren Friis Hansen, Copenhagen Business School
- Michael Svendsen, Royal Danish Library
- Jens Begtrup, Danish National Archives (Until June 2025)
- Anne Sofie Fink, DeIC
- Carina Ollerup Christensen, Aalborg University
- Cecilia Maria Lindberg Laursen, National Archives

12. Appendices

All appendices are here linked to the Zenodo community: [Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation, second mandated period \(from 2023\)](#)

- [Working Group A: Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Full Report 2025](#)
- [Forslag til praksis vedrørende FAIR for statslige fonde](#)
- [Fondskrav til Data Management: En case sammenligning mellem Danmarks Grundforskningsfond \(DG\) og Innovationsfonden](#)
- [Overordnede principper i forhold til sikkerhedsaspekter i relation til National strategi for data-management baseret på FAIR](#)